

Website Creation Exercises and Features Discussion on National Standard School Final Examination Using Algorithm Linear Congruential Generator.

Exercises and Features Discussion Using Algorithm Linear Congruential Generator

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UASBN (National Standard School End Test) is a national exam at the elementary level held after high school and junior high school exams. The subjects tested there are only three, namely Indonesian, Mathematics, and Science. Subsequent UASBN is held for participants who do not take the main exam. Website Creation Training Problem and Discussion Features National Standard School Exams Using Linear Congruential Generator Algorithms. This application will display UASBN problems of the previous year that can be done in order to improve the ability of students in Elementary School level (SD) in doing the actual UASBN problem. This app uses the Linear Congruential Generator (LGC) randomization algorithm to randomize the packets to be performed by students, LGC is a randomization algorithm used in computers, LGC uses a linear model to generate random numbers.

Keywords: System, Application, Exercise Problem, Exercise, LCG, Final School Exam, Application, System, Problem, UAS.

I. INTRODUCTION

UASBN (National Standard School End Test) is a national exam at the elementary level held after high school and junior high school exams. 75% of UASBNs are made by the Provincial Education Office and 25% of the questions are made by BSNP (National Education Standards Agency). UASBN was first held May 12, 2008. The subjects tested there are only three, namely Indonesian, Mathematics, and Science. Subsequent UASBN is held for participants who do not take the main exam. Participants who have not passed UASBN can follow it next year. UASBN year lesson 2013/2014 has been deleted.

Try Out within the scope of education in Indonesia is a test that is usually carried out before the main exam, or among learners

referring to trials before facing the actual exam. Try Out is implemented to support or measure the ability of students in solving problems facing the actual exam.

Based on the problems that occur then this research focuses on the implementation of Website Creation Training Problem and Discussion Feature National Standard School Exam Using Linear Congruential Generator Algorithm. This application will display UASBN problems of the previous year that can be done in order to improve the ability of students in Elementary School level (SD) in doing the actual UASBN problem. Hasanudin University posted related alleged plagiarism book titled Source and Availability of feed raw materials in Indonesia, there are posts and data taken from the article[2]. Plagiarism can be avoided by self-awareness by way of quoting the sources that have been taken but to be more effective in avoiding plagiarism it is necessary to use plagiarism to detect similarities in several documents and scientific papers. Based on the problems that occur then this research focuses on the implementation of plagiarism applications, to minimize the occurrence of plagiarism in the document of scientific work among students in particular. The event of plagiarism is still carried out although it has been inserted that there are sanctions if proven to plagiarism, and with the development of easy technology in doing plagiarism example that can be given is copy-paste to the work

II. METHODOLOGY

n system development of writer use System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) approach that is Prototype model. In making this application, the plan will use Prototyping method. The use of Prototyping method because the paradigm of Prototyping method is information system that describes the important things of information system that will come. In using Prototype method and consists of stages to be done, namely:

1. Needs collection
 - a. Submitted a letter of taking data about UASBN national standard earlier to the Central Jakarta Education Office.
 - b. Mengumpulkan problem given the Education Office.
 - c. Search and read the literature to help build the system.
 - d. Recording the needs of the students and the bibliography.
2. Quick Design

Doing the design according to the information obtained at the time of analysis. Design and Design is done based on the information collected.
3. Build Prototype

Making the application system is done after the design and the concept of the application has been completed.
4. Evaluation of Prototype

Testing apps created with Alfa's Black-box stage method.
5. Repair Prototype

The application has been finished and can be performed repair. Improvements included in fixing errors or damage not found in the previous step.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jeffry L. Byrne, (1997). Microsof SQL Server: What Database Administrator Need to Know. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [2] Ramez Elmasri and Shamkant B. Navathe, (2011). Sixth Edition: Fundamentals of Database System. Boston: Addison-Wesley.
- [3] Bing Liu, (2008). Web Data Mining: Ecloring Hyperlinks, Contents, and Usage Data. Chicago,IL: Springer.
- [4] Fanny Eko Prasajo, (2004). Aplikasi Perpustakaan Berbasis Web Pada SMA Negeri 1 Mlonggo Jepara. Jurnal Jurusan Sisten Informasi, Fakultas Ilmu Komputer, Universitas Dian Nuswantoro.
- [5] Ladjamudin, A. B., (2013). Analisis dan Desain Sistem Informasi. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- [6] Fajar Anugrah Ramadhan. Pembuatan Aplikasi "Online Test" Berbasis Android. Teknik Informasi Jurusan Teknik Informatika dan Komputer Politenik Negeri Jakarta
- [7] Saiful Bahri, Hero Wintolo and Anton Setiawan. Algoritma Random pada Computer Based Test Penerimaan Mahasiswa Baru STTA Yogyakarta. Teknik Informatika STTA Yogyakarta
- [8] Bobby Prasetyo, Inna Agustina dan M. Gufroni, (2017). Perancangan Game Puzzle Pemadam Kebakaran Menggunakan Metode Linear Congruential Generator (LCG). Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science (JOINTECS).
- [9] Atul Mishra, (2014). Critical Comparison Of PHP And ASP.NET For Web Development. International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research